

IMPORTANCE OF BERBERIS (BERBERIS VULGARIS L.), A MEDICINAL PLANT DISTRIBUTED ON THE MOUNTAIN SLOPES OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *In Decree No. PD-3968 of the President of Uzbekistan dated October 12, 2018 "On measures to regulate the field of folk medicine in the Republic of Uzbekistan", Dcree No. PD-4668 dated April 10, 2020 "On additional measures to develop folk medicine in the Republic of Uzbekistan", on November 26, 2020, confirmed. Decree PD-4670 dated April 10, 2020 "On measures for the protection, cultivation, processing and rational use of available resources of medicinal plants growing in the wild". On the basis of the Decree No. PF-139 of May 20, 2022 "On the effective use of the raw material base of medicinal plants, the creation of value chains by supporting processing" it was mentioned that it is important.*

Keywords: *Carotenoids (xanthophyll, lutein, chrysanthemumxanthin, zeaxanthin, auroxanthin, flavoxanthin capsanthin, etc.), carbohydrates, aromatic and pectin substances, organic acids, macro and microelements, vitamins E and C, beta-carotene, "blackberry".*

Introduction. Berberis (*Berberis vulgaris* L.), belongs to the family of black-sugar (Berberis family), belongs to the family of shrubs. The leaves are thick, short-banded, arranged in a row. The flower is yellow, with a double peduncle, collected in a peduncle; the fruit is a berry. Distributed in the Northern Hemisphere, there are 193 species, of which 44 are acclimatized. Zirk leaf contains alkaloids such as berberine, oxycontin, and bermamine. Their fruits are sour, appetizing and tasty, so they are used in the food industry. In Uzbekistan, it is put into pilaf.

It is called "karkand" because it tastes good to the food. In medicine, it is used to treat liver diseases, reduce fever, stop diarrhea, and strengthen the heart system. The fruit is a dietary product with low nutritional value. It has been found that 100 g of it has a power of 29 kcal. The fruit contains carotenoids (xanthophyll, lutein, chrysanthemaxanthin, zeaxanthin, auroxanthin, flavoxanthin capsanthin, etc.), carbohydrates, aromatic and pectin substances, organic acids, macro and microelements, vitamins E and C, and beta-carotene substances. In addition to its beautiful appearance, zirk also has healing properties.

In ancient Greece, it was used as a blood purifier. In Tibet, zinc is believed to be a natural substance that prolongs human youth. It has been widely consumed in our country, its root, trunk and bark are used to stop bleeding and treat various colds. Fruit juice has antipyretic, germ-killing, and bleeding-stopping properties.

Karakand fruit is also recommended for cleansing the body, removing toxins, and slowing down the aging process. In order to prevent liver diseases, rheumatism, urinary tract and kidney colds, it is necessary to eat freshly ripe Berberis fruit with food. Berberis contains the alkaloid berberine, which has sedative properties. This substance also helps people who are trying to get rid of alcoholism and addiction. Pharmacies sell a drug called berberine, which is made from a substance extracted from zinc. This drug is used in the treatment of gallstones and cholecystitis.

Italian scientists, in cooperation with doctors, found that berberine is a practically unparalleled healing agent for people suffering from malaria and swollen kidneys. Indian doctors use berberine to treat severe infectious leishmaniasis.

In the treatment of malignant tumors, a special herbal complex containing zirk fruit is recommended. Berberis bark is included in the medicine called cholelithin, which is prepared for the treatment of cholecystitis, exacerbation of jaundice, gallstone diseases. In China, the bark of the plant is used to treat eye colds, and the root bark is used to open the airways, heal wounds, and treat cancer. Bulgarians use Berberis to treat radiculitis and kidney diseases.

In Poland, Berberis is used to treat hypovitaminosis (vitamin deficiency). The Germans use zirk as a tincture for the treatment of gastrointestinal tract, oral cavity, and lung ailments.

In France, Berberis is recommended as a bactericidal, hypotensive and antimalarial agent. Ripe fruits and leaves can be used to make tea, which is very pleasant and rich in useful vitamins. It is very easy to prepare, for this, take 1 teaspoon of its fruit and leaves, pour 1 cup of boiling water over them and let it steep for an hour. Drink this tea three times a day for two weeks until you get a positive result. In eye colds, eczema, wounds, washing with this decoction or putting a gauze soaked in it on the affected part gives a positive result. In arthritis, rheumatism, radiculitis, leg muscle damage, osteochondrosis, this herbal decoction is drunk as a cold-relieving and pain-relieving agent. Berberis root and leaves decoction: take 1 tablespoon of crushed roots and leaves, pour 1 cup of water over it, boil for 1 minute, let it rest for 30 minutes, pass through a cheesecloth. In case of diarrhea, drink 1 tablespoon 1 hour before meals. Berberis root decoction (applied): pour half a liter of water over 1-2 tablespoons of crushed root, boil for 1 minute, let it rest for 1 hour. In the above-mentioned diseases, a gauze soaked in a decoction is placed on the diseased member and compressed.

It is not possible for women to eat zirk during the days of chilla after the climax and the opening of the eyes. Berberis increases the activity of muscles, therefore pregnant women should not consume it, it may cause premature miscarriage. It can not be consumed by nursing mothers. It is not recommended to be used in cases of gallstones, liver cirrhosis, jaundice, in some personal cases where it is not liked, as well as for children under 12 years of age. It should also be noted that unripe blueberries are poisonous and should not be eaten.

The candy "Barbaris", which we love to eat from time to time, is made from barbaris (the Russian name of the plant) - Berberis. It is also called black sugar.

This plant is widespread in the countries of Eastern Asia, the Caucasus, Central, Eastern and Southern Europe, and Africa. There are more than 500 species of zirk, of which about 100 are acclimatized. On the mountain slopes of Uzbekistan, red sedge and black sedge are common. It grows more in dry and sunny places. Zirk leaves contain berberine, oxycontin, berbamine and other alkaloids. Since their fruits are sour and tasty, they are added to various dishes, including pilaf, and make food delicious. Due to the large consumption of black lemon, it is also called "black lemon" and "northern lemon" due to its color. In medicine, it is used to treat liver diseases, reduce fever, stop diarrhea and strengthen the heart. In ancient times, zirk was widely used as a blood purifier. It is also known that Babylonians and Indians treated many patients with this plant. In ancient Greece, it was used as a blood purifier. Tibetans believed that zinc is a natural substance that prolongs human youth

Names in different countries: Uzbekistan – зирк, USA – barberry, Azerbaijan – zirinc, Hungary – borbolya, Italy – crespino, Vietnam – dã nhân sâm, Georgia- კაჭახტურო, Ireland –

barberry, Spain– bérbero, Kazahstan – бөріқарақат, China- 伏牛, Korea -매자 나무, Mongolia – barberry, Germany – Berberitze, India – दारुहल्दी, Chegue – dřišťál. Italian scientists in collaboration with doctors found that berberine is a practically unparalleled healing agent for people suffering from malaria and swollen kidneys. Indian doctors use berberine to treat severe leishmaniasis. In the treatment of malignant malignant tumors, a special complex of herbs containing zirk fruit is recommended. Zirk root bark is included in the medicine called cholelithin, which is prepared for the treatment of cholecystitis, exacerbation of jaundice, gallstone diseases. In China, the bark of the Zirk plant is used to treat eye colds, and the root bark is used to open the airways, heal wounds, and prevent cancer. Bulgarians use zirk bark to treat radiculitis and kidney diseases. In Poland, zinc is used to treat hypovitaminosis (vitamin deficiency). The Germans use zirk as a tincture for the treatment of gastrointestinal tract, oral cavity, and lung diseases. In France, zirk is recommended as a bactericidal, hypotensive and antimalarial agent.

Ripe fruits and leaves can be used to make tea, which is very tasty and rich in useful vitamins. It is very easy to prepare, for this, take 1 teaspoon of its fruit and leaves, pour 1 cup of boiling water over them and let it steep for an hour. This tea is drunk three times a day for two weeks until a positive result is achieved. In eye colds, eczema, injuries, washing with this decoction or putting a gauze soaked in it on the affected part gives a positive result. In case of arthritis, rheumatism, radiculitis, leg muscle damage, osteochondrosis, a decoction of this plant is drunk as a cold-relieving and ogre-relieving agent. Decoction of roots and leaves of zirk: take 1 tablespoon of crushed roots and leaves, pour 1 cup of water over it, boil for 1 minute, let it rest for 30 minutes, pass through a cheesecloth. In case of diarrhea, drink 1 tablespoon 1 hour before meals. Zirk root decoction (applied): pour half a liter of water over 1-2 spoons of crushed root, boil for 1 minute, let it rest for 1 hour. In the above-mentioned diseases, a gauze soaked in a decoction is placed on the diseased limb and compressed.

Reminder. Taking into account that consumption of zirk increases the activity of muscles during the climax and chill days after childbirth, pregnant and lactating women are not recommended to use it. It is not recommended to be consumed by children under the age of 12 in cases of gallstones, cirrhosis of the liver, jaundice, and in some personal cases where it is not recommended to eat it.

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